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Downscaling climate impacts and decarbonisation pathways in EU Islands, and enhancing socioeconomic and non-market evaluation of Climate Change for Europe, for 2050 and beyond

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Work Package 4: Modelling Climate impacts in 11 EU islands' case studies for 2030- 2100

Deliverable 4.1 – Part B. Report on climatic databases to be used to quantify indicators in the impact chains.

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1. Introduction

This integration to D4.1 aims to present preliminary results obtained by WP4 partners as to the computation of hazard indicators that are relevant for the parallel work of SMTs, with particular attention to the feasibility of their subsequent normalization and use in Impact Chain operationalization. This report must then be considered only indicative of the on-going work of WP4, and as such does not follow the structure of the final deliverable on hazard indicators (D4.3), that will be organized per island and per sector.

2. Preliminary report from UCLM on energy productivity

In this report we show preliminary results in the frame of the WP4 of the SOCLIMPACT project. We calculate a number of indicators related to renewable energy productivity. Indicators are wind and photovoltaic energy productivity, as well as low-productivity periods defined as energy droughts. We have used variables from a RCM (SMHI-RCA4) driven by a GCM (MPI-M-MPI-ESM), from the Euro-CORDEX ensemble. Here we present results for the 1986-2005 period. The model data used in this analysis has a horizontal resolution of 0.11°. Only one of the study regions, the Balearic Islands, is evaluated in these preliminary results.

2.1 Photovoltaic productivity

The present indicator will show potential changes in photovoltaic (PV). Productivity [kWh/kW] is defined as the energy produced in a period of time divided by the power installed, which is considered as unitary. The present preliminary results are only based in mean values of productivity for the period 1986-2005.

2.1.1. Methodology

In order to obtain photovoltaic productivity, surface solar radiation (SSR) and ambient temperature from the climate simulations are used as input variables for a parametric PV model.

The PV modeling process can be summarized in two steps: first, incident solar radiation that reaches solar cells inside the panels is obtained through the decomposition of global solar irradiation and the transposition to the plane-of-array (POA). After that, the electrical performance of the system is modeled. Surface solar irradiation from climate models is equivalent to Global Horizontal plane Irradiation (GHI).

Daily mean of surface solar radiation, SSR, from climate models is decomposed first into the diffuse and direct beam components. The decomposition is made through a regression between the clearness index, which represents the relationship between global irradiation at the horizontal plane and the extra-terrestrial irradiation (Liu & Jordan, 1960), and the diffuse fraction (relationships between the diffuse component and GHI) as in Collares-Pereira (1979).

A daily profile of the irradiance [W/m^2] is obtained which allows to get the different components in the plane of the array. Direct irradiance in the tilted plane is obtained straightforwardly from geometrical criteria.

The diffuse component is obtained using the Hay and McKay model (1985). The effective irradiation is then obtained from the consideration of optical losses due to the incident angle and dust accumulation (Martin, 2001). Only a moderate dust accumulation degree is considered.

2.1.2. Preliminary results

Yearly mean productivity

Figure 1. Photovoltaic yearly mean productivity [kWh/kW] for the Balearic Islands for the 1986-2005 period.

Yearly mean values of around 1500 to 1600 kWh/kW are found over the Balearic Islands for the period 1986-2005. A minimum can be found over the northern part of Mallorca Island, with productivity values below 1450 kWh/kW.

Monthly mean productivity

Figure 2. Photovoltaic monthly mean productivity [kWh/kW] for the Balearic Islands for the 1986-2005 period.

The annual cycle of photovoltaic productivity can be observed in Figure 2. Monthly mean values have a maximum over the islands in July. The range goes from around 90 kWh/kW for winter months to above 150 kWh/kW for summer season.

2. 2 Wind energy productivity

The present indicator will show potential changes in wind energy productivity (Wprod). Here, productivity [MWh/MW] is defined as the energy produced in a period of time divided by the power installed, which is considered as unitary.

2.2.1 Methodology

We first derive the wind speed at surface (10 m) from 6-hourly U_{10} and V_{10} wind components. We calculate W_{10} as:

$$W_{10} = \sqrt{U_{10}^2 + V_{10}^2}$$

Then, we calculate W_{10} at the turbine hub height [$H = 100$ m for wind energy over land; $H = 150$ m. over the sea (not shown here)]. From Tobin et al. (2015):

$$W_H = W_{10} \cdot \left(\frac{H}{10}\right)^\alpha$$

$$\alpha = \frac{1}{7}$$

Once we calculate W_H at the turbine hub height, we later calculate wind potential (Wpot) as in Jerez et al. (2015). However, in order to do that, W_H must be regarded as the average of the wind speed at 6-hours intervals (W_{av}):

$$W_{av} \left(\frac{t_{2i+1}}{2}\right) = \frac{[W_H(t_i) + W_H(t_{i+1})]}{2}$$

$$W_{pot} = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } V < V_I \\ \frac{V^3 - V_I^3}{V_R^3 - V_I^3} & \text{if } V_I \leq V < V_R \\ 1 & \text{if } V_R \leq V < V_O \\ 0 & \text{if } V \geq V_O \end{cases}$$

Being $V_I = 3$ m s⁻¹ (cut-in wind velocity); $V_R = 12$ m s⁻¹ (rated velocity); $V_O = 23$ m s⁻¹ (cut-out velocity) and $V = W_{av}$.

Finally, wind productivity (Wprod) is calculated from the wind potential produced by the 6-hr averaged wind multiplied by the number of hours (6 hours). For daily Wprod, we sum all the four Wpot (one for each 6-hr interval) of the day.

Yearly mean productivity of Wprod is then calculated as the average of the annual sums of daily Wprod within the considered period (e.g. 1986-2005). Monthly mean productivity of Wprod is calculated as the average of the monthly sums of daily Wprod within the considered period (e.g. 1986-2005) and month (e.g. January).

2.2.2. Preliminary results

Yearly mean productivity

Figure 3. Wind energy yearly mean productivity [MWh/MW] for the Balearic Island for the 1986-2005 period.

As shown in Figure 3, Yearly mean values of between 1500 and 2000 MWh/MW are found over the Balearic Island for the period 1986-2005. A minimum can be found over the southwestern part of Mallorca Island, with productivity values below 1500 MWh/MW.

Monthly mean productivity

Figure 4. Wind energy monthly mean productivity [MWh/MW] for the Balearic Island for the 1986-2005 period.

The annual cycle can be clearly observed in Figure 4. Monthly mean values of wind energy productivity have always a minimum over the islands, but winter months show the maximum productivity with values around 250 MWh/MW, while in summer values decrease up to ~50 MWh/MW over the islands.

2.3 Renewable energy productivity droughts

In the context of the SOCLIMPACT project, photovoltaic and wind energy productivity droughts are computed as an indicator of productivity steadiness in European islands.

2.3.1. Methodology

Renewable energy droughts can be regarded as low-productivity periods during which the daily productivity is smaller than a low-productivity threshold. To systematically detect energy droughts, a Deficiency Index (DI) is computed following Raynaud et al. (2018). This is defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} DI(i,j) &= 1 \text{ if } P(i,j) \leq P_o(i,j) \\ DI(i,j) &= 0 \text{ if } P(i,j) > P_o(i,j) \end{aligned}$$

Where P is the daily productivity [kWh/kWp] and P_o the corresponding low-productivity threshold. As in Raynaud et al. (2018), thresholds are computed as a percentage of the mean daily productivity for the examined time period (i.e., 1986 – 2005). Two distinct thresholds are calculated to determine moderate and severe energy productivity droughts, respectively. The moderate energy drought productivity threshold is defined as 0.5 times the mean daily productivity estimated over the entire period of study. The severe energy productivity threshold is set to 0.2 times the average daily productivity instead. According to the above expression, energy productivity droughts occur when the DI is equal to 1. A potential advantage of the energy productivity drought definition from Raynaud et al. (2018) is that, as pointed out by the authors, the DI does not depend on time or the electricity demand. Thresholds to determine future-climate productivity energy droughts will be computed taking the present-day mean daily productivity of the corresponding region.

2.3.2. Preliminary results

Figure 5. Percentage of days of moderate (left column) and severe (right column) renewable energy productivity droughts computed for the 1986 – 2005 time period in the Balearic Islands. Photovoltaic (PV) and wind energy productivity droughts are depicted in the upper and lower rows, respectively.

In Figure 5 we observe that, in the Balearic Islands, for the examined time interval, wind productivity droughts are more prone to occur than solar productivity droughts. For instance, in Mallorca, moderate wind productivity droughts are found nearly 50% of the days, while moderate photovoltaic productivity droughts take a maximum value close to 10 - 12% of the days. Severe solar productivity droughts are rare, but severe wind droughts can even

reach values close to 40% to the NW of Mallorca. Results here shown therefore highlight the more stable nature of solar energy relative to wind energy.

Figure 6. Mean of the yearly maximum number of consecutive days of moderate (left column) and severe (right column) renewable energy productivity calculated for the 1986 - 2005 time period in the Balearic Islands. Photovoltaic (PV) and wind energy productivity droughts are shown in the upper and lower rows, respectively.

Figure 6 shows that, in the Balearic Islands, low wind-productivity periods are longer than low-photovoltaic productivity periods. Whilst in Mallorca the maximum duration of moderate solar productivity droughts is close to 5 - 6 days, moderate wind productivity droughts can extend up to 20 days or

more. This pattern can also be observed in severe droughts. The maximum duration of severe solar droughts is 1 - 2 days, but this can be between 12 and 15 days for severe wind droughts. These results further support that solar energy productivity is more stable in time in comparison to wind energy productivity. The N/NW of Mallorca is more vulnerable to energy productivity droughts.

2.4 References

Collares-Pereira, M., Rabl A. (1979). The average distribution of solar radiation: correlations between diffuse and hemispherical and between daily and hourly insolation values. *Solar Energy*, 22, 155-164.

Hay, J. E. & McKay, D. C. (1985). Estimating Solar Irradiance on Inclined Surfaces: A Review and Assessment of Methodologies. *Int. J. Solar Energy* 3:4-5, págs. 203-240.

Jerez, S., Thais, F., Tobin, I., Wild, M., Colette, A., Yiou, P., & Vautard, R. (2015). The CLIMIX model: a tool to create and evaluate spatially-resolved scenarios of photovoltaic and wind power development. *Renewable and sustainable energy reviews*, 42, 1-15.

Liu, B. Y. H., & Jordan, R. C. (1960). The interrelationship and characteristic distribution of direct, diffuse, and total solar radiation. *Solar Energy*, 4, 1-19.

Martin, M. & Ruíz, J. M. (2001). Calculation of the PV modules angular losses under field conditions by means of an analytical model. *Solar Energy Materials & Solar Cells*, 70, 25-38.

Raynaud, D., Hingray, B., François, B., & Creutin, J.D. (2018). Energy droughts from variable renewable energy sources in European climates. *Renewable Energy*, 125, 578-589.

Tobin, I., Vautard, R., Balog, I., Bréon, F. M., Jerez, S., Ruti, P. M., ... & Yiou, P. (2015). Assessing climate change impacts on European wind energy from ENSEMBLES high-resolution climate projections. *Climatic Change*, 128(1-2), 99-112.

3. Preliminary report from CYI - Standardized Precipitation- Evapotranspiration Index

In the framework of the SOCLIMPACT project, the Standardized Precipitation-Evapotranspiration Index - SPEI (Beguería et al. 2014) is used as an indicator of water availability to be used in the operationalization of the Energy Sector Impact Chains. Preliminary results, presented here, include the calculation of SPEI for one indicative EURO-CORDEX (Jacob et al. 2014) simulation in order to test the methodology we are going to follow (post-processing of model output, calculation of indices, visualization of results). The selected simulation was performed by the KNMI-RACMO22 regional climate model, driven by the HadGEM2-ES global earth system model. The calculation of SPEI was based on the reference period of 1986-2005 in order to investigate if future conditions are expected to deviate from this recent past period which is considered as the “normal”. Following Spinoni et al. (2018), we calculate SPEI at 12-month accumulation scale, a good compromise between short timescales suitable for seasonal events and long timescales suitable for multi-annual cycles. Besides the historical simulation we use the RCP2.6 and RCP8.5 future pathways. Monthly precipitation, maximum and minimum temperature data in a horizontal resolution of 12-km (0.11 degrees) are used. The calculation of potential evapotranspiration is based on the Thornthwaite method (Thornthwaite 1948). Here we focus on the seven Mediterranean island key-regions for SOCLIMPACT (Cyprus, Crete, Sicily, Sardinia, Corsica, Malta and Balearic Islands). At a later stage, we will calculate this drought index for all SOCLIMPACT islands, while an ensemble of regional climate simulations will be used. In the following pages we present the preliminary results for each island.

CYPRUS (CY)

Figure 1. Time-series of the SPEI-12 index averaged for the island of Cyprus for the RCP2.6 (top panel) and RCP8.5 (bottom panel) future pathways.

Figure 2. Maps of the SPEI-12 index for the island of Cyprus for the historical period (left panel), mid-21st century (middle panels) and end of 21st century (right panels) for RCP2.6 and RCP8.5 future pathways.

CRETE (GR)

Figure 3. Time-series of the SPEI-12 index averaged for the island of Crete for the RCP2.6 (top panel) and RCP8.5 (bottom panel) future pathways.

Figure 4. Maps of the SPEI-12 index for the island of Crete for the historical period (left panel), mid-21st century (middle panels) and end of 21st century (right panels) for RCP2.6 and RCP8.5 future pathways.

SICILY (IT)

Figure 5. Time-series of the SPEI-12 index averaged for the island of Sicily for the RCP2.6 (top panel) and RCP8.5 (bottom panel) future pathways.

Figure 6. Maps of the SPEI-12 index for the island of Sicily for the historical period (left panel), mid-21st century (middle panels) and end of 21st century (right panels) for RCP2.6 and RCP8.5 future pathways.

SARDENIA (IT)

Figure 7. Time-series of the SPEI-12 index averaged for the island of Sardinia for the RCP2.6 (top panel) and RCP8.5 (bottom panel) future pathways.

Figure 8. Maps of the SPEI-12 index for the island of Sardinia for the historical period (left panel), mid-21st century (middle panels) and end of 21st century (right panels) for RCP2.6 and RCP8.5 future pathways.

CORSICA (FR)

Figure 9. Time-series of the SPEI-12 index averaged for the island of Corsica for the RCP2.6 (top panel) and RCP8.5 (bottom panel) future pathways.

Figure 10. Maps of the SPEI-12 index for the island of Corsica for the historical period (left panel), mid-21st century (middle panels) and end of 21st century (right panels) for RCP2.6 and RCP8.5 future pathways.

BALEARIC ISLANDS (ES)

Figure 11. Time-series of the SPEI-12 index averaged for the Balearic Islands for the RCP2.6 (top panel) and RCP8.5 (bottom panel) future pathways.

Figure 12. Maps of the SPEI-12 index for the Balearic Islands for the historical period (left panel), mid-21st century (middle panels) and end of 21st century (right panels) for RCP2.6 and RCP8.5 future pathways.

MALTA (MT)

Figure 13. Time-series of the SPEI-12 index averaged for Malta for the RCP2.6 (top panel) and RCP8.5 (bottom panel) future pathways.

Figure 14. Maps of the SPEI-12 index for Malta for the historical period (left panel), mid-21st century (middle panels) and end of 21st century (right panels) for RCP2.6 and RCP8.5 future pathways.

3.1 References

- Beguería S, Vicente-Serrano SM, Reig F, Latorre B (2014) Standardized precipitation evapotranspiration index (SPEI) revisited: Parameter fitting, evapotranspiration models, tools, datasets and drought monitoring. *Int J Climatol* 34:3001–3023. doi: 10.1002/joc.3887
- Jacob D, Petersen J, Eggert B, et al (2014) EURO-CORDEX: New high-resolution climate change projections for European impact research. *Reg Environ Chang* 14:563–578. doi: 10.1007/s10113-013-0499-2
- Spinoni J, Vogt J V., Naumann G, et al (2018) Will drought events become more frequent and severe in Europe? *Int J Climatol* 38:1718–1736. doi: 10.1002/joc.5291
- Thornthwaite CW (1948) An Approach toward a Rational Classification of Climate. *Geogr Rev* 38:55. doi: 10.2307/210739

4. Preliminary report from NOA - Fire Weather Index (FWI)

The FWI system provides numerical non-dimensional ratings of relative fire potential for a generalized fuel type (mature pine stands) based solely on weather observations. The meteorological inputs to the FWI System are daily noon values of air temperature, relative humidity, wind speed and 24h accumulated precipitation. It consists of different components that assess the responses of moisture to atmospheric forcings at different soil depths and then combine these in order to derive fire behavior indices in terms of ease of spread and intensity.

FWI is part of the Canadian Forest Fire Danger Rating System established in Canada since 1971 (van Wagner 1987). Furthermore, since 2007, FWI has been adopted at the EU level and used in a harmonized way throughout Europe by the European Forest Fire Information System (EFFIS) of the Copernicus Emergency Management Service.

It is selected for exploring the mechanisms of fire danger change for the islands of interest in the framework of SOCLIMPACT, as it has been proved to adequately perform for several locations, including the Mediterranean basin (e.g. Viegas et al. 1999; Dimitrakopoulos et al. 2011; Giannakopoulos et al. 2012; Bedia et al. 2013; Karali et al. 2014).

4.1 Data

For the calculation of the index, 3-hourly climatic output from state-of-the-art RCM/GCM pairs, developed within the EURO-CORDEX initiative, have been used. The future period simulations of the models will be based on the Representative Concentration Pathways (RCPs) 2.6 and 8.5. The selected RCM/GCM pairs are the following:

RCA4/ICHEC-EC-EARTH (historical/RCP2.6/RCP8.5)

RCA4/MOHC-HadGEM2-ES (historical/ RCP2.6/ RCP8.5)

RCA4/MPI-M-MPI-ESM-LR (historical/ RCP2.6/ RCP8.5)

These pairs have been selected as the only ones in the EURO-CORDEX database containing 3-hourly climatic output and future realizations for both RCP 2.6 and 8.5.

4.2 Methodology and preliminary results

For the operationalization of the Forest Fires Impact Chain, the FWI for the fire season (defined from May to October) will be calculated. The calculation will be performed for each one of the selected GCM/RCM pairs and their ensemble mean will then be provided for the reference period (1986-2005), as well as the two future periods of interest (2046-2065 and 2081-2100) for the two selected RCPs. Some map examples presenting mean control and future fire season FWI for the Mediterranean region are presented in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1: Mean fire season FWI for the control period 1986-2005 (upper), for the near future period 2046-2065 (lower left) and for the distant future period 2081-2100 (lower right).

Next, in order to provide information on sub-island level, the index will be recalculated over municipalities and, finally, it will be normalized to be used as the hazard input for the risk calculations through impact chain operationalization, as can be seen in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Normalized mean fire season FWI values on municipality level for the current climatic conditions (1986-2005) for the islands of Corsica and Sardinia.

4.3 References

- Bedia, J., Garcia, S. H., Camia, A., Moreno, H. M., Gutierrez, J. M., 2014: Forest Fire Danger Projections in the Mediterranean Using ENSEMBLES Regional Climate Change Scenarios', *Climatic Change* 122 (1-2), doi:10.1007/s10584-013-1005-z.
- Dimitrakopoulos, A. P., Bemmerzouk, A. M., and Mitsopoulos, I.D., 2011: Evaluation of the Canadian fire weather index system in an eastern Mediterranean environment, *Met. Apps*, 18, 83-93, doi:10.1002/met.214.
- Giannakopoulos, C., LeSager, P., Moriondo, M., Bindi, M., Karali, A., Hatzaki, M., and Kostopoulou, E., 2012: Comparison of fire danger indices in the Mediterranean for present day conditions, *iForest*, 5, 197-203.
- Karali, A., Hatzaki, M., Giannakopoulos, C., Roussos, A., Xanthopoulos, G., and Tenentes, V., 2014: Sensitivity and evaluation of current fire risk and future projections due to climate change: the case study of Greece, *Nat. Hazards Earth Syst. Sci.*, 14, 143-153, <https://doi.org/10.5194/nhess-14-143-2014>.
- van Wagner, C. E., 1987: Development and structure of a Canadian forest fire weather index system, *Forestry Tech. Rep.* 35, Canadian Forestry Service, Ottawa.

Viegas, D. X., Bovio, G., Ferreira, A., Nosenzo, A., and Sol, B., 1999: Comparative study of various methods of fire danger evaluation in southern Europe, *Int. J. Wildland Fire*, 9, 235–246.

5. Preliminary analysis of extreme events: Sea Surface Temperature, Wind Speed and Total Precipitation

In D3.3 indicators for extreme events are generally defined as the number of events exceeding a fixed threshold in a determined period of time (e.g. number of days with Wind speed maximum above the 98th percentile of a reference baseline period or Number of days per year in which Temperature is above than 90th percentile of maximum daily temperature). Such threshold can be either dictated by expert judgment for a specific field of application (e.g. maximum SST tolerated by fish species in aquaculture), or inferred through statistical analysis of data probability distributions.

This paragraph shows different examples of the application of the foregoing definitions, highlighting possible limitations in their application, in particular when comparability of indicators across different locations is to be achieved via normalization techniques.

5.1 Sea Water Heat Waves: reference threshold for Sea Surface Temperature derived from expert knowledge

Heat waves occur when the daily maximum temperature exceeds some fixed threshold for more than N consecutive days, where N depends on the field of application. They can be traced either in air temperature or in sea temperature, with the aim to monitor possible risks for health or negative impacts on tourism fluxes, or in sea surface temperature, in order to evaluate the stress exerted on farmed species.

Within SOCLIMPACT, the corresponding indicator has been defined as the number of consecutive days N with daily average SST above the maximum tolerable temperature for the fish species (NSSTX). This definition allows counting the number of events per year, their persistence and their inter-annual variability over longer time windows. However, discussion within the Aquaculture Sector Modelling Team highlighted that both N and the temperature threshold are species-dependent, so this preliminary analysis has been carried out using the temperature threshold (25 C) over which the optimal accretion of sea bass is impaired, according to expert knowledge. The threshold in SST was

raised to 300 K (27 C approx.), in order to account for the variation of temperature with depth between the surface and the fish cages. Results must be considered as only indicative of the method and of its limitations, while more accurate work and specific analysis for each island will be carried out after data collection by Island Focal Points and further work within the SMT.

Figure 1 shows the mean, minimum and maximum of duration and number of events per year, as estimated for the period 1980-2100 from the high resolution (10 km approx.) CNRM simulation of the Mediterranean circulation available from the MED-CORDEX database. This simulation was chosen as it is one of the few that covers both RCP2.6 and RCP8.5, and the only one currently available (more will be added during the progress of SOCLIMPACT). Figure 2 and Figure 3 are Figure 1 counterparts for RCP2.6 and RCP8.5, respectively.

It is evident that on average both the number of events and their duration are observed to increase under both scenarios. However, the data are characterized by high variability and intermittency, both in time and space, even more than the maps of minimum and maximum values (not necessarily occurring at the same time at different locations) are capable of showing, due to the soothing effect of graphical interpolation. For this reason, average values must be carefully handled, while the “spotty”, uneven nature of the fields possibly impairs any normalization exercise and synthetic comparison across islands.

Nevertheless, the “event counting” approach can deliver valuable practical information to stakeholders when locally applied to one dimensional time series, at sites where actual plants/farms are located, and is expected to prove useful in assessing potential economic impacts and in inferring possible adaptation strategies.

Figure 1

Figure 2

mean duration of events per year – rcp 26 – 2040–2060

mean number of events per year – rcp26 – 2040–2060

minimum duration of events per year – rcp26 – 2040–2060

minimum number of events per year – rcp26 – 2040–2060

max duration of events per year – rcp26 – 2040–2060

max number of events per year – rcp26 – 2040–2060

Figure 3

mean duration of events per year – rcp 85 – 2040–2060

mean number of events per year – rcp85 – 2040–2060

minimum duration of events per year – rcp85 – 2040–2060

minimum number of events per year – rcp85 – 2040–2060

max duration of events per year – rcp85 – 2040–2060

max number of events per year – rcp85 – 2040–2060

5.2 Extreme wind speed: reference threshold derived from statistical properties of data distribution

The Nearest Rank method has been applied to the regional CNRM-SMHI simulations for RCP4.5 and RCP8.5, in order to compute the number of days per year in the 2040s for which the 98th percentile of the baseline period 2000-2005 is exceeded. Results are shown in Figure 4 and 5 for each scenario, together with the corresponding change with respect to the constant reference value of 7.305 days per year corresponding to the 98th percentile for the baseline period. Figure 6 shows the 98th percentile wind speed thresholds for the baseline period. Despite the limited extension of the reference time window, results are consistent with the expected overall decrease in wind speed over the Mediterranean region, with the exception of the extreme eastern basin and of the Black Sea, that has been already documented in literature (Davy et al., 2018, FEMIP Report, 2008). However, pooling all data together and therefore mixing low and high wind speed values without allowing for any internal time variability (e.g. seasonality) can lead to underestimating effective tail thresholds, limiting the practical relevance of the observed changes in the indicator, which need to be thoroughly discussed within SMTs, also keeping in mind the possible limitations to the normalization of data already discussed in the previous paragraph.

Figure 4

NWiX98 RCP4.5 2040s

NWiX98 RCP4.5 2040s

Figure 5

NWiX98 RCP8.5 2040s

NWiX98 RCP8.5 2040s

Figure 6

Surface wind speed 2000–2005

5.3 Extreme precipitation: application of extreme value distributions

The Gumbel distribution of extreme values (Gumbel, 1958) has been employed to analyse daily total precipitation fields from historical and RCP8.5 simulations carried out with the SMHI regional model RCA4 driven by two different GCMs (MPI-M-MPI-ESM-LR and MOHC-HadGEM2-ES). The resulting return levels for different prescribed return times (40, 20, 10 and 5 years) are shown for Corsica and Sardinia in Figures from 7 to 14, which all indicate an increase in the expected extreme values under the RCP85 scenario, although the magnitude of return levels can significantly differ across model chains. Only for the 40-year return time, the analysis has been applied to the seasonal maxima, confirming the increments, although with different behaviours across seasons (Figures from 15 to 18). It is worth noting that such analysis, although based on the statistical properties of the data, is more flexible with respect to the chosen thresholds and produce smoother 2D fields that can be normalized without excessive difficulty. The analysis can be further applied to 3-hourly precipitation fields in order to trace cloudbursts that potentially represent more severe hazards than the smoothed daily precipitation maxima.

Robustness of results can be assessed by comparing the relative changes in return levels across models (Figures 19 and 20, for the near (2046-2065) and the far (2080-2100) time horizons), as to sign and magnitude.

Whenever meaningful thresholds are available from expert knowledge, the extreme value analysis can be inverted to yield the expected return times for the selected threshold, which can be related to the pay-back times of investments in the potentially affected economic sectors (Figures 21 and 22 - selected conventional threshold = 70 mm/day).

Due to the limited size of the statistical sample, all the results of the presented analysis obviously need to be checked against the selected statistical distribution (Gumbel, GEV, Pareto, etc.) and as to their sensitivity to thresholds, keeping in mind that extrapolation for return times longer than twice the selected time window are not feasible.

Figure 7 - 1986-2005 – Return Levels for $Q_t = 40$

Figure 8 - RCP85– Return Levels for $Q_t = 40$ yrs

Figure 9 - 1980-2000 - Return Levels for $Q_t = 20$ yrs

Figure 10 - RCP85 - Return Levels for $Q_t = 20$ yrs

Figure 11 - 1986-2005 – Return Levels for $Q_t = 10$ yrs

Figure 12 - RCP85 – Return Levels for $Q_t = 10$

Figure 13 - 1986-2005 – Return Levels for $Q_t = 5$ yrs

Figure 14 - RCP85 – Return Levels for $Q_t = 5$ yrs

Figure 15 - 1986-2005 -MPI – Seasonal distribution of Return Levels for $Q_t = 40$ yrs

Figure 16 - 2081-2100 – MPI – RCP85 – Seasonal distribution of Return Levels for $Q_t = 40$ yrs

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Figure 17 1980-2005 – MHOC-HC - Seasonal distribution of Return Levels for $Q_t = 40$ yrs

Figure 18 - 2080-2099 – MOHC-HC – RCP85 – Seasonal distribution of Return Levels for $Q_t = 40$ yrs

Figure 19
MPI

RCP85 NEAR - $Q_t = 40.0000$ years - % change in Return Levels

RCP85 FAR - $Q_t = 40.0000$ years - % change in Return Levels

Figure 20
MOCH-HC

RCP85 NEAR – Qt = 40.0000 years – % change in Return Levels

RCP85 FAR – Qt = 40.0000 years – % change in Return Levels

Figure 21
MPI - 1986-2005

MPI RCP85 - 2081-2100

Figure 22
MOHC - 1986-2005

MOHC RCP85 - 2080-2099

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5.4 References

Davy et al, 2018: Climate change impacts on wind energy potential in the European domain, Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews Volume 81, Part 2, 1652-1659, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2017.05.253>

FEMIP Report, 2008: Climate Change and Energy in the Mediterranean, Plan Bleu Regional Activity Center, planbleu.org/sites/default/files/publications/changement_clim_energie_med_en.pdf

Gumbel E.J., 1958: Statistics of extremes, Echo Point Books and Media, LLC; ISBN 978-1-62654-987-6

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